

Zik's Neo-Welfarism: A Viable Option for Nigerian State

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ABSTRACT

The study explored the relationship between African philosophers and their contribution, focusing on Nigeria political philosopher Nnamdi Azikiwe and his contribution in neo-welfarism. He made a comparison between capitalism, welfarism, neo-welfarism, and he sought to ascertain the most relevant democratic models suitable for Nigeria politics. He proposes an ideology “neo-welfarism” for Africa, Nigeria in particular where the state need to monitors, manage and directs the economic affairs for the welfare of each individual of the state, where there will be fair and equitable distribution of the country’s goods among the citizens and avoid the situation whereby some citizens will be extremely rich and others will be extremely poor.

KEY WORD: NEO-WELFARISM, CAPITALISM, SOCIALISM, WELFARISM.

INTRODUCTION

This study is aimed at describing Azikiwe’s perception of Nigeria's problems and to appraise the extent to which his Neo-welfarism ideology provides solutions to Nigeria. The love of good patriotism is fading, our government is rooting our economy, citizens are denied their rights, and masses are suffering. Government jobs are no longer by merit or academic excellence, and the last of it now, our education is now meaningless, because it has been polluting with evils. Institutions where rich children sort lectures for good grades, while the poor masses are denied their rights. Our government mismanaged funds and resources meant for the development of our state.

Bad leadership, corruption, and embezzlement are caused by poverty of ideologies, which has eaten deep into our society's life, and has affected our reasoning and thinking. Azikiwe presents Neo-welfarism ideology as the solution to these problems. The government shall not be above the law, and fundamental human rights shall be guaranteed. Neo-welfarism will help us avoid capitalist nonchalant attitude towards social injustice, and the socialist degradation of human beings who are reduced to thoughtless, purposeless nonentities made to function as puppets and marionettes of the constituted authority. Thus, Azikiwe suggested that Neo-Welfarism should be adopted by the Nigerian government, which will be most suitable for solving our contemporary challenges of economic development.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The problem encountered in the Nigeria state is poverty of ideology. The rich keep getting richer, while the masses are suffering. This is the reason; Zik's presents Neo-welfarism as the outcome of the good element of the different ideologies and economic doctrines on the principle of eclectic-pragmatism. That, which will permit private enterprises, invites the state to participate and collaborate in their management, control and sponsorship in order to achieve the best welfare for the people and development of Nigeria.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The purpose of the study in this paper is to provide general information that Neo-welfarism should be adopted by the Nigerian government, which is most suitable for solving the contemporary challenges of economic development and to alleviate the some problems facing Nigeria.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

Firstly, the objective of the paper is to find out the linkages between the socio-economic ideologies and secondly, the impact of Neo-welfarism to the Nigeria state.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The research does not over labour itself with discussing various socio-economic systems obtainable in all countries, to locate the best option for Nigeria. It is rather focused on Neo-welfarism with little insights into Capitalism, Socialism and Welfarism.

The work will explain these above-mentioned socio-economic systems giving their merits and demerits and, stating why each is not suitable for Nigeria when taken alone. Neo-welfarism will be equally explained bringing out why it is the most viable option for the Nigerian state.

METHOD OF THE RESEARCH

In this paper, the data that the author used are mainly historical and exposition. The method employed in the study is expository. The data are extracted from the socio-economic systems: capitalism, socialism and welfarism, by combining together to reach a final conclusion on what we believe to be good elements of Neo-welfarism.

This method is found to be useful and helpful, now Nigeria is facing an economic and political crisis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The end of colonial rule in most countries in Africa has not resulted in a complete control of their socio-economic or political affairs. They are sovereign states only in name. In reality, many of them remain under the socio-economic (capitalism, socialism, welfarism and political control of their former rulers. As can be seen from the history of many African countries, the achievement of political or flag independence does not automatically lead to socio-economic independence because, as Boateng rightly observed:

Owing to the greatly superior economic and technological advantages which the developed nations enjoy, they are still in a position to determine or even to dictate to a large extent, the economic fortunes of the developing nations which depend on them for the very things, such as Capital goods, technical know-how and entrepreneurial skills, which they need in order to modernize and upgrade their fragile economies¹

Neo-welfarism has much relevance in the socio- political and economic life of man. By this fact, effort will be made to practically apply the principles of neo-welfarism for the growth and development of our Nigerian society.

Although most of our erudite thinkers agree that what can lead Nigeria and Africa as a continent out of this extremely complex or tortuous structure, is the adoption of an effective and efficient socio-political and economic ideology.

According to Nkrumah, “the essence of neo-colonialism is that the nation which is subject to it is, in theory, independent and has all the outward trappings of international sovereignty. In reality its socio-economic system and thus its political policy is directed from outside”²

However, this situation was later to be changed with the advent of scholars who came back from overseas training and education. With this new force in place, European exploitation, subjugation and domination met its match. The first half of the twentieth century witnessed the biting wind of nationalism that blew across the African landscape.

Thinkers like Nnamdi Azikiwe, Kwame Nkrumah, Julius Nyerere, Obafemi Awolowo and other shaving completed their studies abroad came back home and began nationalist movements that was aimed at putting a stop to the physical occupation of African nations by the Europeans – colonialism in Africa. In order for this movement to gain momentum, the African scholars began with endeavor to reclaim the original consciousness of the African identity. This paper appraises the contributions of Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe to African socio-political and economic growth during the twentieth century. The paper concludes after a thorough appraisal that emerging African leaders should understudy the socio-political and economic philosophy of the late sage, which if well implemented could bring about the much desired good governance and sustainable socio-political growth in the continent before the end of the 21st century.

They packaged this idea in the formulation of various theories. Some of these theories are discussed hereunder:

Philosophical Consciencism, Nkrumah (1909-1972)

Kwame Nkrumah was a socialist revolutionary philosopher. He was very critical of capitalism. Omoregbe sees capitalism “as a refined form of feudalism, which in turn is a refined form of slavery”³.

Capitalism is therefore a developed and refined form of slavery.

“For Nkrumah original men lived communalistic lives, all land belonged to the community, everything was owned by the community, including all means of production, and everyone worked for the common good of the community”⁴.

But gradually people began to claim ownership of property and hence, inequality, slavery, feudalism, capitalism and class struggle crept in. The bourgeois then came up with a theory to support their stand.

In reaction therefore, he believes that the traditional African society is not capitalist in nature, but egalitarian and communal. He then calls on African nations to reject capitalism and then embrace socialism, which gets its strength from the egalitarian and communal living in African society. He amplified the call to reject inequality, individualism, capitalism and imperialism forcefully brought into Africa by the European imperialists by adopting socialism for the Africans to go back to their roots.

Consciencism is the philosophical and ideological system of Nkrumah for the decolonization of the African continent. The basis of this philosophy is materialism, in this sense, materialism does not preclude the existence of immaterial or spiritual realities, it only affirms the primacy of matter, and maintains that spiritual realities developed from matter through a dialectical tension inherent in matter. Nkrumah’s philosophical consciencism was seen by many as answer to the problems posed by three dominant identities: the traditional indigenous identity, the Islamic element and the Euro-Christian element. Hence, Nkrumah’s consciencism was regarded as a philosophical synthesis.

Negritude, Senghor’s (1906-2001)

Leopold Senghor was a renowned poet and philosopher. His philosophy of negritude is well understood when the policy of assimilation by the French government was in focus. Assimilation

policy was aimed at assimilating Africans into French culture and citizenship. This therefore implies the rejection of African culture, African values, African identity, African personality and African attitude as worthless.

Africans were expected to consider it an honor to be allowed to adopt the French culture and become French citizens at the expense of their African culture and identity. “Senghor’s negritude is the rejection of this policy of Assimilation and exaltation of African culture, values and identity”⁵.

Senghor found solidarity in a common black identity. He believed that a change could be achieved through a shared black heritage. Senghor believes Africans have a distinctive outlook toward life and a distinctive cultural identity.

As such, like Nkrumah he believes individualism and capitalism are foreign to traditional African society and culture. For example Omoregbe believes “feelings and sentiments take precedence over abstraction in the African way of life”⁵.

The African is deeply religious and gives prominence to the spiritual dimension in his outlook on life. “He has no individualistic mentality since the society in which he lives is structured on communalism and not individualism or capitalism”⁶.

“Negritude is therefore a philosophical theory of re-discovery, re-awakening, re-direction, a philosophy of emancipation and mental decolonization in order to give the pride of place to African culture and identity”⁶.

What Asouzu in the 50th inaugural lecture of the university of calabar may view as the product of error of judgment in the maxim; “The nearer the better and safer”⁷.

His endeavor was to make the Africans see their unique identity and culture as distinct from their European counterparts.

Ujamaa, Nyerere’s (1922-1999)

This is the philosophy of the Former President of Tanzania, Julius Nyerere, he believes that capitalism and individualism is foreign to African and therefore his philosophy is based on the communal nature of African society. “Nyerere also still believes that socialism based on class

struggle, conflict and tension is just as foreign to African traditional society as capitalism, and therefore should be jettisoned”⁸.

At this point Nyerere is different from Senghor, who believes that class struggle, tension and conflict is part of universal law of progress. “For Nyerere traditional African society is not based on tension and class struggle but on “family-hood”, that means family relationship”¹⁸.

Nyerere believes that is the root of authentic African socialism. For this to be applied to the whole African society in this modern times, Nyerere believes that the family-hood has to be extended beyond the extended family, beyond tribe, beyond the immediate society, beyond one African nation, it must be made to extend to reach the whole of African countries and for him African socialism has to base on this. “Nyerere envisages a society made up of atomic family units, a country made up of Ujamaa villages, a kind of “family villages” with mutual cooperation and collaboration. Such a nation would be basically family units extended to embrace the whole society”⁹.

The capitalistic spirit of acquisition, individualism, the exploitation of man by man, class struggle and conflicts will all be excluded from society. Inequality will be eliminated and everybody will be prepared to work for the good of the community in any capacity. For Nyerere, when exploitation, colonialism and inequality are removed from the society, the individual feels liberated and liberation, for him, is development.

African Socialism, Awolowo (1909-1987)

Obafemi Awolowo was born in 1909 in Ikenne, ijebu Remo in Western Nigeria. He was a journalist, an active legal practitioner, politician and educationist.

He studied commerce and law at the University of London. The Honourable society of the inner Temple called him to the Bar in 1946, in London. Awolowo actively practiced law between 1946 and 1951.

He established the daily newspaper “Nigeria Tribune” in Ibadan in 1949, a medium that would later promote his political party; the Action Group of Nigeria to be founded later in 1951. He was elected into the Western House of Assembly in Ibadan in 1951, where he served till 1959. He was leader of Government Business, Western Nigeria and the Local Government and Finance between 1951-1954, the premier of western Nigeria from October 1954 to December 1959, when he gave it up because of the opposition in the federal parliament.

In 1960, he became a member of the Federal House of Representative in Lagos, until 1962 when he was arrested, charged and convicted of treasonable felony for ten years imprisonment. He was released in 1966 and made federal commissioner for Finance, which lasted till 1971 under General Gowon (during and after the Nigeria-Biafra war).

Awolowo actively vied for the presidency in the second Republic of Nigeria under the unity Party of Nigeria. Till his death, he desired restlessly to lead Nigeria as her president. His major political works are Path to Nigeria Freedom (1947), Thoughts on Nigerian constitution (1966), The People's Republic (1968), the strategy and Tactics of the People's Republic of Nigeria (1970), and The Problems of Africa (1977).

As an eminent thinker with deep prophetic insight, Chief Obafemi Awolowo (also known as Awo) is a convinced and uncompromising advocate of socialism. In his political life he has consistently been on the left wing and the critical side in an essentially capitalist society. If there is any Nigerian thinker whose ideas have influenced the lives of millions of people, it is Obafemi Awolowo. As a politician he has not been very successful, but as a philosopher and thinker he has been most influential and most successful. Awolowo distinguished between the primary aim of a state and its ultimate purpose. The primary aim, according to him, is the maintenance of internal order and the prevention of external aggression.

The ultimate purpose of a state is to enable its citizens to enjoy the fruits of their labor, and to live a full and happy life, including the enjoyment of the fundamental human rights. In his efforts to live a full and happy life, man has adopted two well-known economic systems, with separate and distinct polarities. They are the capitalist system and the socialist system. Awo then goes on to analyze these two systems, beginning with capitalism.

The essential characteristic of the capitalist system, Awo says, is economic freedom. Capitalism has four postulates, namely, private property, choice, equality and egoistic altruism. It protects by law the right of the individual to own as much private property as he can acquire. The individual is given complete freedom of choice to use "his energy and property as he thinks fit subject only to the restraint imposed by law"¹⁰.

He went on to explain that everyone is entitled to work, live and freely contract on the basis of equality with others. Awo concedes, however, that capitalism has had some achievements to its credit. Among such achievements are the fact that it encouraged science and technology. For it

was the capitalists who provided funds for scientific research, and eventually brought about the industrial revolution. It was the capitalists who brought about the overthrow of feudalism and the abolition of slave trade¹¹.

So much for the achievements of capitalism. In the capitalist ruthless struggle the casualties always outnumber the survivors by far. Nature has endowed the earth with natural gifts in such a way as to make human beings economically interdependent. But the capitalists have thwarted this design of nature by greedily and selfishly appropriating to themselves alone nature's free gifts to all men. It is an evil system that encourages the rich to become richer and the poor to become poorer.

The gap between the rich and the poor becomes progressively wider with the passage of time. Here, capitalism sows the seeds of discord among people and legalizes stealing. The workers in a capitalist system are unjustly treated in the distribution of the nation's wealth. For they are denied their fair share.

Capitalism clearly goes against the principles of dialectics and this means that it is doomed to failure. It is a thesis which produces its own antithesis, namely, the working class who are really the gravediggers of capitalism. The conflict between the thesis and the antithesis in the capitalist system is bound to result in the synthesis of socialism. Dialectics, according to Awo, begins with thoughts, words and deeds are dynamic. The lesson which history has taught mankind is that like causes always produce like effects. Man always reaps what he sows. Anybody who sows evil reaps evil. While good proliferates and flourishes, evil withers away and becomes extinct.

Awo says his own brand of socialism differs from that of Marx and Engels. For these latter socialism is a stage between capitalism and communism.

Its principle is from each according to his ability and to each according to his deeds and it is characterized by the dictatorship of the proletariat. Having suppressed the masses under capitalism, the capitalist are in turn also suppressed by the proletariat under the socialist system. This is a stage in the dialectical process of the evolution of society. Eventually, the socialist stage will be superseded by communism which is a stage of social perfection. Besides, Awo thinks that the idea of a stateless society is unrealistic. There never will be a time when man will not need the state. For it is only within the state that man can enjoy personal freedom and a happy life. All the means

of production should be vested in the state; those already in the hands of individual citizens should be confiscated by the state and the owners fairly compensated.

THE CONCEPT OF NEW-WELFARISM

Biography of Nnamdi Azikiwe

No thinker can be properly understood without understanding the historical and cultural setting in which he lived; Azikiwe is not an exception. This makes it pertinent to take an in-depth look at his biography for proper appreciation of his thoughts.

From a humble background, Nnamdi Azikiwe was born on Wednesday, 16th November, 1904 in Zungeru, present Niger State, in North-central Nigeria to the family of Mr. Obededom Chukwuemeka Azikiwe and Mrs. Rachael Chinwe Azikiwe. Both parents were Igbo, indigenes of Onitsha, in the present Anambra State, South-eastern Nigeria. At the time of his birth, his father was a staff of the colonial government, and worked as a clerk with a section of the military Department, the Nigerian Regiment, which constituted a unit of the British West African Frontier Force located at Zungeru, in what was then Wushishi District of Niger Province in the Northern Protectorate of colonial Nigeria. “The young Nnamdi lived the first eight years of his life (1904-1912) in Zungeru, where he learnt and became conversant with the Hausa language, which shaped his life, and more importantly imbibed in him tolerance for differing views and culture from a tender age”¹².

The educational career of the young Nnamdi began at Onitsha, his paternal home, where he commenced his first primary education at the Holy Trinity School of the Roman Catholic Mission in 1912. For Christian denominational reason, being a protestant by faith, his father ensured that he was moved from the Catholic Mission School to a school owned by one of the Protestant denominations. Consequently, between 1912 and 1915, the young Nnamdi attended many primary schools for denominational reasons. Agbafor Igwe argues that during this period, the young Nnamdi, as a roving student “changed school as often as his civil servant father was transferred from one place to another”¹³. This constant change of school in his formative years later broadened his Christian viewpoint, as he experienced many Christian denominations and their diverse doctrines.

In 1915, Nnamdi Azikiwe relocated from Onitsha and joined his parents, then resident in Lagos, where he continued his primary education as he was in 1916 enrolled into the Methodist Boys' High School to continue his primary education shortly after his arrival from Lagos (Igwe¹⁴). Shortly thereafter, he continued his educational career at Onitsha, later moved to Calabar in 1920, and was trained at the Hope Waddell Training Institute, Calabar, where he was influenced and inspired by some students he met there. Specifically, "Nnamdi Azikiwe emphasized the inspiration from a story told him by his classmate, an indigene of the Kru ethnic group, Liberia, that in Liberia the President and all the governors in the countries were blacks; all the judges, law officers and heads of departments in the civil service were blacks too (Azikiwe,)"¹⁵. This story had a fascinating effect on Nnamdi Azikiwe, who from then made up his mind to devote his life to the redemption of the black man.

Nnamdi Azikiwe left Hope Waddell in 1920 for Wesleyan Boys' High School, Lagos where he continued his education and was inspired by the sermon of Dr. (Rev.) James Emmanuel Kwegyir Aggrey of the Gold Coast (Ghana) resident in the United States. Other than the sermon, Dr. Aggrey had told the congregation about his personal life which revealed sacrifice for Africa and mankind at large. He further highlighted to the congregation that "nothing but the best is good for Africa (Azikiwe)"¹⁶.

It was from then that Nnamdi Azikiwe began to think of furthering his education in the United States.

While at Wesley Boys High School, in December 1920, he excelled in his studies and won a prize for which he was given a book on the biography of James A. Garfield, a former President of the United States, who rose from grass to grace. The book galvanized the young Nnamdi, who was just sixteen years, as he became more determined to succeed in life. His wish to embark on the trip to the United States to further his education did not materialize in 1920, and thus he had to write the Civil Service Entrance Examination in 1921.

He was successful in the examination and was employed as a clerk in the Nigerian Treasury in Lagos and worked there from 1921 to 1924. Nnamdi Azikiwe worked as a staff of the Treasury Department for a few years; but his belief that education was the key to advance in Africa propelled him to seek admission in many higher institutions in the United States. He gained admission, and

in 1925 he officially (his earlier attempt to travel to the US failed) left Nigeria to attend Storer College, West Virginia, United States.

Zik left the shores of Nigeria in 1925 to Storer College, Harpers Ferry, West Virginia, United States where he did his preliminary courses that lasted from 1925-1926.

He enrolled there for his bachelor degree programme between 1926 and 1927, but later moved on to Howard University, Washington D.C in February, 1928, where he continued his degree programme. However, for financial reasons, he was unable to complete his undergraduate studies at Howard, which necessitated his application for admission and financial assistance from Lincoln University, Chester County, Pennsylvania. The applications were granted by authorities of the university, and thus Nnamdi Azikiwe bagged a Bachelor of Arts honors degree in Political Science from Lincoln University in June 1930. Zik had earlier in 1927 obtained a Certificate in Law from the Lasalle Extension University, Chicago. He also obtained a Certificate in Journalism from Teachers College, Columbia University in 1930.

He also obtained two Masters Degrees while in the United States: a Master of Arts degree in Religion and Philosophy from Lincoln University in 1932 and a Master of Science degree in Anthropology from the University of Pennsylvania in 1933. After a brief stint as Instructor of Political Science at Lincoln from 1933 to 1934, Nnamdi Azikiwe left the shores of the United States to his motherland, Africa. As he aptly captures his decision to return to Africa in these words: "Then I made my decision to return to Africa"²⁶. I was ready to continue suffering personal inconvenience, if need be, in order to do for Africa what that continent needed for a renaissance in thought and action. Motivated by an inner force to succeed thus far, I was resolute in my determination to press forward towards a new Africa (Azikiwe,)"¹⁷.

Azikiwe withdrew from active politics in 1966 when the Army took over power, but emerged again in 1979 for the Presidency of the second Republic and was unsuccessful. He assumed the position of an experienced adviser and elder in African nationalism till his death in 1995. Among his most notable Political Publications are: *Renascent Africa* (1937); *Liberia in World Politics* (1938); *The African in Ancient and Medieval History* 1938; *Political Blueprint of Nigeria* (1942); *Zik: A Selection of Speeches* (1961); *Tribalism: A Pragmatic Instrument for National Unity* (1964); *Ideology for Nigeria: Capitalism, Socialism or Welfarism?* (1981).

Zik's Examination of Major Political System

Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe (also known as Zik) is not just a politician, he is also a political philosopher. "Azikiwe starts his teaching on ideology with a critical examination of the credibility and workability of the three well known socio-political systems; capitalism, socialism and welfarism"¹⁸. Both intellectually and in practical life Zik has amply demonstrated his preference for the via media, that is, the way of compromise.

His preference for the via media has led him to embrace eclecticism in his political philosophy. The dialectics of eclecticism, he believes, lead to the harmony of opposites.

Having critically examined the major political systems, capitalism, socialism, welfarism, Zik finds each of them wanting. But none of them, in his view, is totally bad without some good elements. He therefore works towards a harmonization of these systems by combining what he believes to be the good elements in each of them. The result of this is what he calls "neo-welfarism"¹⁹.

Capitalism

Dr. Zik describes capitalism as a socio-economic system essentially based on private ownership of capital goods or means of production. It is profit-oriented and profit motivated. In a capitalist society, capital goods may be owned either by individuals or by groups of people who form limited liability companies. Capitalism means an economic system characterized by private or corporation ownership of capital goods, by investments that are determined by private decision, rather than by state control, and by prices, production and distribution of goods determined mainly in a free market. Thus, the goods are sold in a "free market"²⁰. In a capitalist society, the means of production including land, factories, machinery and natural resources are owned and controlled by individuals, and not the state.

Essential Features of the Capitalist System

In his critical analysis of Capitalism, Azikiwe identifies three essential features of the capitalist system. These essential features of capitalism include, first, private ownership of capital goods; second, investment motivation by the desire for maximization of profit; and third, a free market without governmental control. Following his close analysis of capitalism, Zik describes a capitalist society as follows:

When a person lives in an economic system that is characterized by private ownership of capital goods, whose production, distribution and prices are determined by him, motivated solely by the profit he envisages to make in the bargain, in a free market and without unreasonable state interferences, we say that such a person lives in a capitalist society²¹.

Expatriating further on the essential characteristics of capitalism, he explains that the private ownership of capital goods implies that such goods may be owned either individually or corporately, as a result of the foresight and enterprising capacity of the persons concerned.

Zik says that investment motivation by the desire for the highest possible profit implies that the person or persons making the investment do so voluntarily without state control apart from the ordinary legal processes. The main reason for investing their capital in the business venture is to enable them to earn maximum profit.

Zik also explains that a free market without state intervention means that the manufactured product is sold at a price which is fixed by the factors of supply and demand, in addition to the cost of production, distribution, and the management of the commodities sold, including labor, all solely determined by the owners of capital goods.

The Merits of Capitalism

In his analysis of the merits of the capitalist system, Zik identifies five main arguments of the advocates of capitalism: diffusion of power, specialization of labour based on a free-market economy, competition as an incentive to efficiency, the capacity for risk-bearing, and the provision of a minimum standard of social security.

Diffusion of power

The advocates of the private ownership of the means of production argue that capitalism makes for diffusion of power in society. It is held that the ownership of productive property implies power over the lives of many people.

The advocates of capitalism feel that instead of the state “owing such property and exerting unlimited power over many people, such power should be diffused among many property owners”²².

Free Market Economy

The advocates of capitalism argue that the capitalist system is based on specialization of labour under a free market economy, so that each worker freely chooses to make his own contribution through his skill and output. They point out that a free market economy is sharply contrasted with a ‘command market economy’ which “subjects individuals where to work, what to do, what to produce, what price to charge, what to eat, what to invest and what to save”³².

They conclude that a free market economy is much more natural and preferable to a command market economy because “the one is voluntary and democratic; the other is mandatory and authoritarian”²³.

Competition as an Incentive

Capitalists argue that competition, which is an essential characteristic of a free market system, is an incentive to efficiency and competition, which implies the idea of bargaining between the seller and the buyer, gives incentive for the production of better products, lower prices, and better services, which would ultimately lead to a higher standard of living for the people.

Capacity for Bearing Risks

Advocates of the capitalist system argue that capitalists bear unforeseeable risks for society with respect to their business.

They point out that although the profit motive has been inherent in human nature all over the world, throughout the annals of humankind, it coexists with risk-bearing because entrepreneurship is not only for the maximization of profit but also the capacity for bearing.

Minimum Social Security

Zik presents Galbraith as pleading in a sort of apologetics for capitalism, that “an affluent society would, no doubt, secure to all who needed it the minimum income essential for decency and comfort and, to guarantee each family a minimum standard of social security”.

Socialism

Finding capitalism unsatisfactory, Zik turns to socialism. Socialism is essentially characterized by public ownership (state controlled) of the means of production, distribution and exchange. It aims at organizing the state as a fraternal, co-operative commonwealth, with fair and equal distribution of wealth; it aims at realizing a classless society, it rejects class-division and a laissez-faire philosophy. Socialism aims at owning, managing and controlling the means of

production, distribution and exchange. “It seeks to extend its activities to all undertakings with the objective of promoting equality and social welfare. It is altruistic in its content in that it desires expansion of state activities not for aggrandizement but in order to assure freedom and justice to the individual”²⁴. Zik quotes the Soviet Union’s delegation to World Social Economic Congress held in Amsterdam in August 1931:

“Socialism is a system of society in which all the means of production belong to the society as a whole. The socialization of the means of production naturally signifies the abolition of classes and of all class distinctions. Under socialism the whole economy of the country becomes one huge single enterprise, it has been asserted that social economic planning is an essential prerequisite for the existence of socialist economy, just as anarchy of production, and competition are the essential forms of the existence of capitalist economy”²⁵.

The Essential Features of Socialism

In his critical analysis of socialism, Azikiwe identifies the four cardinal points of socialism as follows: promotion of public welfare, fair distribution of wealth, nationalization of public utilities, and the need for scientific planning. Furthermore, he explains that the aim of socialism is to organize the community as a political body and transform it as an instrument of power for owning and managing land, capital and the means of production, distribution and exchange. Many advocates of socialism maintain that socialism is antithetical to capitalism.

The Merits of Socialism

Zik identifies the chief merit of socialism as “the focusing of the spotlight on the need to reform the capitalist system”²⁶. In the light of the above merit, Zik agrees that socialist thought has succeeded in arousing common consciousness that at present, most capitalist countries have transformed into what may be described as socialist societies.

The municipalization of transport, e.g. TRACAS (Transport Corporation of Anambra State) and the common ownership of public utilities were uncommon by the end of the nineteenth century. Today many capitalist states have nationalized land and enacted laws vesting the state with the ownership of mineral rights. A typical example is the Land Use Decree in Nigeria.

The advocates of socialism maintain that one important aspect of socialism that should not be overlooked is economic planning. Under this system, the planning of the whole of the natural economy is not only possible, but absolutely essential. It can be asserted that social economic planning is an essential prerequisite for the existence of a socialist economy.

The Demerits of Socialism

Azikiwe in his critical analysis of the socialist system identifies that socialism, in theory and practice, is interwoven with social, economic, and political issues. He therefore concentrates his criticism of the system on these aspects of group living. Zik identifies socialism as a crusade against poverty. From the political angle, socialism is identified as a struggle to wield power in order to ensure freedom from want and freedom from fear. From the social point of view, socialism is a movement against social injustice and social inequality.

From the economic point of view, critics of socialism maintain that the collective ownership of property is contrary to human nature and argue that this accounts for why the change from capitalism to the socialist system is usually accomplished by the use of force in commandeering private property of the individual members of society.

Furthermore, another weakness of socialism, according to Zik, is the multiplicity of the schools of thought which propagate it, some of which split into sects, factions, and denominations resulting in multifarious bands of socialism.

Welfarism

Welfarism is a “social system where the state assumes the primary responsibility for the individual and social welfare of its citizens. It is the complex of policies, attitudes and beliefs, which animate the state to provide its inhabitants with minimum standards in education, health, housing, pensions, rehabilitation, etc. where individual means are inadequate, (Seldon and Pennance)”²⁷. “When any state protects and promotes the social and economic well-being of its inhabitants, through systems of laws and institutions establishing national insurance against unemployment, industrial accident, ill-health, old age, and destitution, it may be regarded generally as a demonstration of welfarism”²⁸.

In a welfarist state free education and free health care are made available to all the citizens. Thus the welfarist state aims at bringing the greatest good to the greatest number by providing essential services to its citizens virtually free of charge.

Zik commends welfarism for its goal but warns that it has its inherent problems arising from its provision of essential services free of charge. Once it becomes known that these services are free, he points out, there is bound to be a mad rush of people to take advantage of these free services. Zik says this was his experience when, as Premier of Eastern Nigerian, he introduced free primary education. “As soon as news was disseminated that primary and elementary education would be FREE, and fees would no longer be paid, a deluge encompassed my government in the form of widespread surge”²⁹. It is part of human nature, Zik contends, to seek to reap where one has not sown. Zik thus admits that welfarism does help to solve some of the problems created by capitalism, but it cannot eliminate these problems altogether. He therefore finds welfarism inadequate and unsatisfactory. Azikiwe sees the possibility of making good out of the best of these three systems to forge a new system for Nigeria.

Neo-Welfarism

Azikiwe defines it, thus, as: an economic system which blends the essential elements of capitalism, socialism and welfarism in a socio-economic matrix, influenced by indigenous Nigerian mores, to enable the state and the private sector to own and control the means of production, distribution and exchange, whilst simultaneously enabling the state to assume responsibility for the social services, in order to benefit the citizens according to their needs and officially-specified minimum standards, without prejudice to participation in any aspect of the social services by voluntary agencies.

Neo-welfarism as a suitable system for Nigeria, according to Azikiwe, should be based on two schools of thought: eclecticism and pragmatism which themselves are based on rationalism and empiricism. Since the idea of combining elements of capitalism and socialism was practiced by our ancestors and it worked for them, then it is practicable. Zik describes his political philosophy as pragmatic and eclectic. Eclecticism is a term used in philosophy to identify a composite system of thought which blends opposite views.

A neo-welfarist society will be made up of ingredients from capitalism, socialism, and welfarism, “but it will not be capitalist; it will not be socialist, and it will not be welfarist. Rather

it will be a harmony of opposites atop of our external family system to further the frontiers of state responsibility for the welfare of all its citizens”³⁰. While combining the good elements of capitalism, socialism, and welfarism, neo-welfarism will avoid the capitalist non-chalant attitude towards social injustice, and the socialist degradation of human beings who are reduced to thoughtless, purposeless nonentities made to function as puppets and marionettes of the constituted authority. Neo-welfarism will allow private ownership of property, and private enterprise, reinforced by state participation in the private sector. It will recognize and encourage the profit motive as an incentive to the development of individual initiative. But it will not allow the official attitude of laissez-faire which leads to the exploitation of men by their fellow men.

By way of conclusion, one may note that Azikiwe’s neo-welfarism could be an answer to the confused political set-ups in most African states caused by colonial and other influences. As a viable system, it could restore the basis for a genuine African socio-political life, by allowing the positive and workable principles of capitalism, socialism and welfarism to fecundate the root-principles native to African culture.

Dialectics of Neo-Welfarism

Zik describes neo-welfarism as an ideology which is “a vernal and dynamic interpretation of welfarism and its synchronization into a social matrix of the last elements in the universally recognized ideologies of capitalism, socialism, and welfarism. Simpliciter, neo-welfarism embraces belief in private enterprise, reinforced by state participation in the private sector and state collaboration in management technology for completely and efficiently administering on a profitable basis statutory corporations and parastatals, commercial enterprises including government-controlled and government-sponsored companies”³¹. Based on a fundamental law (the constitution), the neo-welfarist state shall be a democratic state in which individual liberty and equality before the law shall be guaranteed. To ensure the stability of the state there shall be checks and balances in the system. Consequently, the neo-welfarist government shall be made of four arms, namely, the Electorate, the Legislative, the Executive, and the Judiciary. It will be the prerogative of the Electorate to decide who shall be the members of the legislative assembly while it will be the members of the legislative assembly while it will be the prerogative of the latter to enact laws and to approve or repudiate the activities of the Executive. The Judiciary for its part shall have the prerogative of reviewing the acts of both the legislative and the Executive to ensure

that they are in line with the Fundamental Laws of the land-the constitution. But, on the other hand, the Legislative and the Executive shall enjoy the prerogative of endorsing or rejecting the appointment or dismissal of the members of the Judiciary.

The foreign policy of the state shall be based on six pivots, namely pragmatic neutrality, good neighborliness, positive reciprocity, search for world peace, zonal or continental cooperation, and the international fellowship based on fair-play, legal equality and mutual respect.

Without being a military state, the neo-welfarist state shall maintain very strong armed and security forces consisting of an army, a navy, an air force, prison services, service corps, a militia, an intelligence agency, a fire service and a legion. The members of these ten categories of forces shall be well-disciplined, highly educated and well-equipped.

In the neo-welfarist state, the government shall not be above the law, and fundamental human rights shall be guaranteed. These shall include the right to life, the right to human dignity, the right to personal freedom, the right to privacy, the right to education, the right to own private property, the right to fair trial, freedom of expression, freedom of thought, freedom of conscience, freedom of religion, and freedom of the press. The government shall have no right to deprive any citizen of his private property “unless such property is required by the state for clearly defined public purposes absolutely and on condition that a fair and adequate compensation shall be paid to the owner of the property”³². Nobody shall be prosecuted in court for committing an alleged offence “unless under due process of law”³³. Nobody in the neo-welfarist state shall be ostracized as an outcast, and nobody shall be denied access to justice in the courts of the land. If within a month a case is not brought against any suspect who is detained, such a person shall be discharged. Everybody shall be presumed innocent until proven guilty. Nobody shall be punished for an offence committed by another person. There shall be no trial in camera in the neo-welfarist state; all trials must be in public and they must be free and fair.

Aims and Objectives of Neo-Welfarist State

In brief, the aims and objectives of neo-welfarism in Nigeria are to restore democracy by building a new political leviathan where there will be political freedom, economic security and social equality, categorized in part as follows.

- (a) To restore and refurbish the instruments of power, in the light of our experience in the political development of Nigeria, since the attainment of independence.

- (b) To be staunch in our attachment to the Rule of Law and not to deviate there from accepting during a period of emergency declared by two-thirds of the membership of the supreme legislatures of the Federation.
- (c) To restore and reinforce the Fundamental Rights of the Nigerian as entrenched and guaranteed in the Nigerian Constitution, without temporization or equivocation or derogation
- (d) To be dedicated in applying the universally recognized principles of the Separation of Powers between the Executive, Legislature, and the Judiciary.
- (e) To be positive and consistent in maintaining the balance of power and not to disturb the equilibrium in the checks and balances implicit in the exercise of executive, legislative and judicial powers.
- (f) To revive popular confidence in the integrity of Government by faithfully enforcing the laws and precepts of the land without compromise
- (g) To be competent, efficient, progressive and ubiquitous in the organization and administration of
 - i. Public Utilities, in providing Nigerians with potable water, electricity, public transport (by road, rail, air, inland waterways and coastwise), and postal and telecommunications
 - ii. Welfare Services, in providing health centres (including maternities, hospitals, mortuaries and asylums), rehabilitation Centres for the physically handicapped: the blind, deaf, dumb, and lame, old peoples' homes; and for the able bodied: the walf, the maimed, juvenile delinquents, ex-convicts and beggars.
- (h) To adopt an open door policy in relation to the production, manufacture, fabrication, distribution, exchange (that is, the important and exportation) of capital and consumer goods, including basic, secondary, ancillary and auxiliary industries, in addition to other factors essential to our economy, like plant and machineries, tools and equipments for our agriculture, forestry, mines and allied industries, food, building materials, new and second hand clothing, paper and newsprint, books and periodicals, stationeries, and other materials and commodities which should enhance the physical satisfaction and economic prosperity of our people, bearing in mind the need to maintain a healthy balance of trade in our international economic relations.

- (i) To tailor our taxation policy on a graduated scale to the extent that Nigerians should pay not more than ten per centum of their net income as direct tax; and no incorporated company operating in Nigeria should pay more than one-third ($33^{1/3}\%$) of its net profit as direct companies income tax.

Canons of Neo-Welfarism as a Political Ideology

Having stated our aims and objectives, as a diagnosis of our social ills, which illustrate that neither capitalism or socialism nor welfarism per se can prevent or cure them permanently, I will now enunciate what should constitute canons of this ideological reorientations as norms and criteria to influence the policies and programmes of our future regime.

“I have in mind the following canons: national unity, federalism, democracy, individual freedom, constitution, rule of law, natural justice, fundamental human rights, revision of laws, legislature, executive, judiciary, checks and balances, international relations, international obligations, armed and security forces, allocation of revenue, public debt, nationalization, social security”³⁴.

These canons of neo-welfarism sum up what activates my beliefs in the practicality of this blueprint for the emancipation of Nigeria from the slavery of alien ideologies and the shackles of our traditions which had made a great country to lack the drive in building a strong, prosperous and powerful nation, all set to instil its nationals with discipline and an abiding faith in their potentialities as a world power.

By adhering scrupulously to these canons, we should prevent the existence of want in the midst of plenty and cure the co-existence of a class of HAVES and HAVE-NOTS.

- (1) **National Unity:** We should believe in the unity of Nigeria based on the equality of all its linguistic components, large and small, before the law.
- (2) **Federation:** It should be our manifest desire to operates in word and in deed a federal system of government, which should insulate both majority and minority groups of Nigerian nationality from wrong-doing either against each other or by the Federal or State or Local Government
- (3) **Democracy:** We should support the principles and practice of democracy to imply the government of the people of Nigeria, by their duly accredited representatives, who shall be

popularly elected, directly, through the secret ballot, periodically, by a democratically constituted electorate, for the peace, order and GOOD government of Nigeria.

- (4) **Constitution:** We should regard the Nigerian Constitution as the Fundamental Law of Nigeria, which binds all the nationals of Nigeria in a political concord. We should hold it to be an article of faith that all legal enactments, enforceable in Nigeria, by whatever names are called, shall be consistent with the Nigerian Constitution; otherwise, they must be null and void and of no effect.
- (5) **Individual Freedom:** We should have an inflexible faith in the sanctity of individual freedom under the rule of law, made by the National Assembly, in accordance with the precepts stipulated by the Nigeria Constitution.
- (6) **Legislature:** We should confirm that it is only by free discussion in a constitutionally established deliberative assembly that the will of the electorate shall be made manifest. Consequently, we should concede the right of the majority and minority parties to express their opinions, either in favor of any measure or against the same, without Victimization. We should safeguard the right of the Opposition Minority to have its say by dissenting from official policy, and the right of the Government Majority to have its way.
- (7) **Executives:** Consistent with the provisions of the Nigerian constitution, we should maintain that the President, assisted by his/her Ministers, should have the exclusive jurisdiction to formulate policy and be vigilant to ensure that a competent and efficient Public Service and parastatals institutions implement same, without prejudice to the absolute and vicarious responsibility of the President for all acts done for an on behalf of the Government.
- (8) **Judiciary:** We should adore and protect the independence of the judiciary as the interpreter of our fundamental and organic laws. To this end we should ensure that only experienced persons of integrity and courage, with the requisite learning and knowledge of our laws shall be secure in their appointment to this hallowed arm of the state.
- (9) **Checks and Balances:** To ensure political stability, we should maintain a steady balance of power among the four arms of the State, namely: the Electorate, the Legislature, the Executive, and the Judiciary. The Electorate should decide who shall be members of the Legislative assembly. The Legislature shall enact legislation and also give assent or

repudiate the activities of the Executive. The Judiciary shall review the acts of the Legislature and the Executive to ensure that they are not ultra vires the Nigerian Constitution. The Executive and Legislature shall endorse or reject the appointment or dismissal of members of the Judiciary.

(10) **International Relationship:** We should formulate and implement a foreign policy based on this;

(a) Pragmatic Neutralism, by which we mean an adaptable co-existence in the comity of nations that is reasonable and practicable in the light of Nigerian experience, in our national interest.

(b) Good Neighborliness, by which we imply friendly relations with our near and remote neighbors.

(c) Positive Reciprocity, by which we infer a relationship that is mutually reciprocal. That is 'you do me ah do you'.

(d) World peace, by which we contemplate co-existence among nations, based on mutual respect, goodwill and fellowship, without resort to armed conflict.

(e) Commonwealth Fellowship, by which we reaffirm our faith in the Commonwealth as an association of state based on historical ties and circumstances.

(11) **International Obligation.** We should negotiate accede to or ratify, international agreements, covenants, conventions, treaties (whether bilateral or multilateral), etc. designed to ensure world peace, preservation of fundamental human rights, protection of our mundane environment from pollution, development of cultural, economic, educational, scientific, and technical co-operation, and the promotion of trade, commerce and industry, on the basis of fair-play, legal equality and mutual respect.

Political Freedom for Nigeria under Neo-Welfarism

Under neo-welfarism, the people of Nigeria should be guaranteed a lawfully constituted government which shall not be above the law, but shall safeguard for the citizens a reign of law and order, based on natural justice, rule of law, and respect for the fundamental human rights, embodied in a written constitution, whose provisions shall be precisely worded and consistent with the above recited canons of this ideology. No person shall be above the law. Our laws shall be

applicable to all persons and the court shall not be precluded from exercising its constitutional jurisdiction over any act by any person or by the constituted authorities of Nigeria.

Rule of Law

The Nigerian Constitution as the fundamental law of the country cannot be transcended by any government or organ of the state or any person.

It must not be violated or debauched. I define the rule of law generally to mean the expression of the will of those who govern with or without the consent of a democratically constituted electorate. In the case of the former, it is a parliamentary act, in the case of the latter, it is an authoritarian decree.

Specifically, it should be understood to mean that this ideology commits itself that Nigeria should be ruled in accordance with the Nigerian Constitution and the laws enacted under its aegis by a legislature whose members were elected by a democratically constituted electorate, based on the secret ballot.

Natural Justice

The people of Nigeria, comprising variegated linguistic groups, are part and parcel of mankind. Therefore, Nigerians are objects of, and subject to, natural phenomena, one of which is the dispensation of justice that is ethical, equitable and fair. The Nigerian Constitution has delineated the norms for dispensing justice according to the rule of law. Nigerian Customary Law has stipulated principles for settling disputes among indigenous folk of non-Christian and non-Muslim faith, on the basis of conciliation and appeasement. Nigerian Sharia Law has laid down precepts for adjudicating issues of personal law among the adherents of Islam.

Therefore, the substructure of Nigerian law and procedure is natural justice which must be recognized as the over-riding factor in our legal system, categorized among others as follows:

- (a) **Hear the Other Side:** No person shall be condemned, reprimanded, punished or convicted of any offence without being given an opportunity to defend him/herself.
- (b) **Arraignment in Court:** No person shall be arraigned in court for committing an alleged offence unless a case has been stated for the person concerned to answer, under due process of law that is consistent with the Nigerian Constitution.
- (c) **Abrogation of Ostracism:** No person shall be ostracized in Nigeria. It is a debauchery of human dignity. Ostracism should be jettisoned as a vestige of our pristine past.

- (d) **Access to Justice:** No person shall be denied access to justice in our duly constituted courts of law with jurisdiction to interpret our Constitution Law, Statute Law, Customary Law, Sharia Law, Military Law or any other law in force in Nigeria.
- (e) **Delay of justice:** No person shall suffer any wrong or inconvenience due to delay in dispensing justice. It is the duty of the state to discharge any person suspected of committing an offence.
- (f) **Presumption of Guilt:** No person shall suffer any form of punishment for all alleged offenses simply because he is presumed to be guilty.
- (g) **Prevention Detention:** No person shall be detained involuntarily by an official except during a declared period of emergency, according to the Nigerian Constitution, and under due process of law.

3.4.3 Fundamental Human Rights

We should venerate and defend with all the constitutional means at our disposal, in accordance with due process of law, that is consistent with the letter and spirit of the Nigerian Constitution, the Fundamental Human Rights entrenched therein, as a bulwark of the liberty of the Nigerian citizen.

By ‘the letter’ of the Nigeria Constitution I mean it's printed version. By ‘the spirit’ of the Constitution I mean any act that is capable of condoning any process that could impugn or paralyze the following fundamental rights:

- (a) **The Right to Life:** No person shall be deprived of life by any person or tribunal, except by a duly constituted court of law.
- (b) **The Right to Human Dignity:** No person shall be subjected to torture, degrading or inhuman treatment. No person shall be held in slavery or servitude or be compelled to do forced labor.
- (c) **The Right to Personal Freedom:** The person of any Nigerian shall be inviolate.
- (d) **The Right to Trial and Appeal:** No person shall be denied or deprived of the right to a fair hearing in a duly constituted court of law or any adjunct tribunal; provided that the right of appeal is consequential.
- (e) **The Right to Privacy:** The privacy of any person, including his/her person, home, property, correspondence, telephone conversation, telecommunication of a private

- nature, personal affairs and those of his immediate family shall be insulated from encroachment by official meddlers or unofficial interlopers.
- (f) **Freedom of Thought, Conscience, Opinion and Religion:** No person shall be denied or deprived of the right to think freely, to believe anything, to hold and entertain any opinion, to practice any religion, without being molested or persecuted, provided that in exercising this fundamental rights, no person shall infringe the norms of civilized living or disturb the public or private nuisance or annoyance or any other punishable offence.
- (g) **Freedom of Expression:** No person shall be denied or deprived of the right to absorb knowledge or ideas and to receive information generally, or specifically on the activities of Government.
- (h) **Freedom of the Press:** No person shall be denied or deprived of the right to print or publish newspapers, periodicals, magazines, annuals or receive news or comments, or to process, digest, disclose, interpret, analyze, criticize, communicate, transmit any publish same by means of the printed word or any other mechanical or electronic device.
- (i) **Freedom of Peaceful Assembly:** No person shall be denied or deprived of the right to assemble freely and associate voluntarily with others for cultural, social, economic, and political and any other legitimate purpose, including the right to form clubs, societies, co-operatives, trade unions, and political parties.
- (j) **Freedom from Discrimination:** No person shall be discriminated against on account of one's place of origin, race, linguistic affinity, sex, religious belief or affiliation, political opinion, etc.
- (k) **Derogation of Fundamental Rights:** Whensoever the National Assembly shall declare a state of emergency in the nation, according to the provisions of the Nigerian Constitution, the enjoyment of the above recited fundamental rights shall be derogated and nullified to the extent of the limitations imposed upon them by the appropriate measures taken by the constituted authorities legitimately authorized by the Constitution to do so.

Economic Security for Nigeria

Under neo-welfarism it should be mandatory for the state to provide avenues of employment for its nationals. The main channels open to the state are the Armed and Security Forces, the public services and the parastatals, in co-operation with the private sector. As envisaged above, the enlargement and maintenance of a mighty Armed and Security Force should absorb a considerable number of unemployed male and female citizens who should be prepared to labor in any sector of our economy, be it agricultural, industrial, and mining, construction, public utilities, etc.

The Right to Employment

In waging the war against want and poverty, the problem of unemployment must be successfully tackled by the state. In a fuller study of this subject in one of my forthcoming books, I have analyzed the causes, effects and results of unemployment. Suffice it for me herein to emphasize the right of the citizen to work and earn an honest living.

Dovetailing the right to work with the right to education, once the citizen has attained the age of twenty-one, the state should provide him/her with gainful employment, depending upon the skill acquired. Otherwise, the induction into the Armed and Security Forces should facilitate the acquisition of skill and thus avoid the embarrassment of the state confronting the problem of an agglomeration of unemployable citizens with its attendant repercussions.

The Right to Public Utilities

By using the expression 'Public Utilities', I mean printing and bindery, radio and TV broadcasting, postal services, telecommunications, transport (including bus and taxicab transit service, boulevards, inter-state highways, railways, bridges, ports and inland waterways), electricity, fuel, newspaper publishing, Federal and State secretariats, etc.

Each State Government should provide at its capital the following

- (a) A printing works and bindery
- (b) A daily newspaper
- (c) A central radio and TV broadcasting station
- (d) A Federal Agency building of four storeys in the form of a quadrangle to house all Federal Ministries operating in the State.
- (e) A State Secretariat of four storeys in the form of a quadrangle to house its various Ministries.

- (f) A regular airport.
- (g) Five electric power stations; and
- (h) Five fire-fighting stations situated at five points of the compass in the state capital.

Each Urban and Rural Local Government should provide at their headquarters the following

- (a) A printing works and bindery
- (b) A weekly periodical
- (c) Five post offices each with automatic telephone exchange situated at five points of the compass located at their respective headquarters.
- (d) A State Secretariat in the form of a quadrangle of three storeys to house the departments of the Local Government.
- (e) A branch of the State radio and TV broadcasting services
- (f) A fire-fighting stations
- (g) Fire electric power sub-stations
- (h) An airstrip in the Urban headquarters with helicopter landing stage in the rural in headquarters,
- (i) A bus transport and taxicab service for intra-State transit
- (j) A wharf or jetty to be constructed on a selected site on the bank of towns in all riverine areas of Nigeria.

3.5.3 The Right to Leisure

The word 'leisure' is generally understood to mean time free from any regular work or duties. It implies the time to spare for repose, rest and relaxation from the humdrum of contemporary civilization. Its synonyms include spare time, convenience, vacant moment, of duty, vacation, furlough, sabbatical leave, ease, etc. if we follow the advice of physicians, leisure helps to prolong life by easing stress, tension and hypertension with their ancillary maladies of a neurological nature with complications affecting the blood vessels and the heart.

Since leisure conduces to the enjoyment of life, and the first fundamental rights in the Nigerian Constitution is the right to life, neo-welfarism attaché's great importance to leisure, and it should be mandatory for the state to provide avenues for the citizen to enjoy a degree of leisure commensurate with good living. The State should make it compulsory for every worker to have a vacation of at least two weeks annually in addition to the public holidays. Each State and Local

Government of the Federation should provide public hotels, amusements and entertainments throughout the country to enable its residents to enjoy leisure at minimum cost.

Each State Government should provide at its capital the following amenities for the leisure of the inhabitants thereof;

- (a) One first class hotel, situated at its capital, with 200 rooms and suites.
- (b) One auditorium-cum-cinema theatre to seat 5,000 spectators.
- (c) One park (open space) of fifty hectares
- (d) One sports center with the following adjuncts: a stadium with a seating capacity of 40,000 including a hostel to accommodate 200 guest athletes; a standard swimming pool; a gymnasium; a boxing ring; twelve tennis courts; one cricket oval with seating capacity of 500 and standing capacity of 2,500; an artificial lake of 50 metres by 500 metres by two metres for rowing and canoeing; a firing range for rifle shooting and a velodrome for cycling.

Each Rural Local Government should provide at its headquarters the following

- (a) One second class hotel or catering rest house with fifty rooms and suits.
- (b) One auditorium-com-cinema theatre to seat 2,500 spectators.
- (c) One park (open space) of twenty-five hectares.
- (d) One sports center with the following adjuncts: a stadium with a seating capacity of 25,000 including a hostel to accommodate 200 guest athletes; a standard swimming pool; a gymnasium; a boxing ring; twelve tennis courts; one cricket oval with seating capacity of 100 and standing capacity of 1,000; an artificial lake of 30 metres by 300 metres by two metres for rowing and canoeing; a firing range for rifle shooting and a velodrome for cycling.

AZIKIWE'S NEO-WELFARISM: A VIABLE OPTION FOR NIGERIA STATE

Neo-Welfarism as an ideology for Azikiwe, is “a vernal and dynamic interpretation of welfarism and its synchronization into a social matrix of the last elements in the universally recognized ideologies of capitalism, socialism and welfarism. Simpliciter, neo-welfarism embraces belief in private enterprise, reinforced by state participation in the sector and state collaboration in management technology for completely and efficiently administering on a profitable basis statutory corporations and parastatals, commercial enterprises including government-controlled and government-sponsored companies”³⁵.

Neo-welfarism as a political philosophy is eclectic and pragmatic. As eclectic it incorporates ideas selected from the systems; hence a composite system of thoughts. It does not modify but it blends opposite views. It is not syncretic since it does not attempt to reconcile the irreconcilables. As pragmatic, it works to the advantage of the many when assessed by its practical results.

Azikiwe via his philosophy sought a society that

“Will not be capitalist; it will not be socialist, and it will not be welfarist. Rather, it will be a harmony of opposites atop of our eternal family system to further the frontiers of state responsibility for the welfare of all citizens”³⁶.

A neo-welfarist state by combining the good elements of capitalism, socialism and welfarism will avert the evils in these systems. Thus, in Neo-welfarism, the free competition of capitalism, which acts as an incentive to efficiency, is moderated by socialism’s emphasis on communal interest and the welfare of all as seen in welfarism.

Most importantly, for Azikiwe, neo-welfarism is based on traditional African society. To ensure stability of the state there shall be check and balance. Thus, the neo-welfarist government should be made up of four arms: the Electorate, the Judiciary, the Executive and the Legislative.

In terms of social service, a neo-welfarist government shall aim at fair and equitable distributions of the country’s good among the citizens and avoid the situation whereby some citizens are extremely affluent while others are in object penury. The state provides essential social services; the citizens are obliged to contribute ‘a fair computed tax’ to the state.

Azikiwe as an anthropologist maintained that no human society, primitive or sophisticated, is culturally naked and that ideology is based on culture. He thought that pristine African society is not barren ideologically. He also said that the responsibility of the present generation of Africans, with particular reference to Nigeria, is to indulge in ideological reorientation (not ideological imposition) in the present maze of ideological wilderness and political instability. In other for Azikiwe to propose an ideology for Africa, Nigeria in particular, he reasons that after a keen examination of the seeming intractable problem of ideological reorientation, he has come to the conclusion that the best that can happen to the continent and country in particular in this regard is the blending of modern foreign ideologies with our pristine indigenous ideologies.

In the neo-welfarist society the state monitors and directs the economic affairs for the welfare of each individual of the state. Although the government does not remove its economic interests altogether in the neo-welfarist state, it participates in making goods and services abundant and affordable for its citizens.

Also the governments in neo-welfarist states direct the people's participation in economic activities forestalls the exploitative tendencies of private individuals. Some individuals have the option to produce better goods of their own at affordable prices in order for them to remain in business contention. Thus Azikiwe neo-welfarism ideology for Nigeria has far-reaching economic and political implications for the freedom of individuals as well as the society. The political aim of this neo-welfarism is to restore democracy by building a new political leviathan where there will be political freedom, economic security and social equality. The role of the state in neo-welfarism will neither be illiberalism nor autocracy anymore that it will be indifferentism.

Under neo-welfarism, human beings will be like brothers, not wolves, in an atmosphere of peace, security and prosperity; the poor and weak, due to historical accident, will co-exist with their more privileged brethren without fear of enslavement. Thus neo-welfarism is a philosophy, and an ideology as well as an economic doctrine which is expected to guarantee; political, social, economic, and spiritual equilibrium, thereby marrying extended family system with the best efforts of non-Nigeria countries to safeguard freedom from ignorance; freedom from anarchy and freedom from lawlessness.

After the study of three foreign ideologies – capitalism, socialism, and welfarism – Azikiwe decided that the best option is neo-welfarism. This involves adapting modern ideologies of alien extraction to the indigenous ideology, which had enabled our forebears to conquer the elements.

Zik's Neo-Welfarism a Re-Oriented Nigeria Ideology

Reorientation connotes an adaptation of principles and facts. Azikiwe believes that our traditional ideology is more pragmatic, because it is a blending of the capitalist with the socialist systems. However, he points out that “it was primordial and was not intended for a complex society in a sophisticated civilization”³⁷.

But he upholds it as coming closer to the concept and practice of the ideal welfare state. He therefore believes that “what Nigeria needs is an ideological reorientation”³⁸ which involves

the blending of our traditional ideology with the best elements in capitalism, socialism, and welfarism, through eclectic and pragmatic principles.

In the process of his ideological reorientation, Zik briefly summarizes the chief characteristics and the main evils of capitalism, socialism, and welfarism as a prelude to his formulation of neo-welfarism.

The private ownership of capital goods, he says, characterizes capitalism; by investments that are determined by private decisions rather than by state control. It is an instrument of private enterprise through which production prices and distribution are determined in a free market. An essential feature of capitalism is the profit motive, which emphasizes individual welfare at the expense of the community. The main evil of the capitalist system is that the citizens live in want in the midst of plenty. Thus it tends towards affluence of the few and poverty of the many based on a laissez faire attitude by the state.

Socialism, he says, is characterized by public ownership of the means of production, distribution, and exchange.

Its main feature is the emphasis on public welfare, whereby everybody is given an equal opportunity to develop their talents and the wealth of society is fairly distributed. The evils of socialism, according to Azikiwe, include the fact that methods of control and planning tend towards regimentation, totalitarianism, and bureaucratic inefficiency.

The road which leads to the socialist paradise is divided into such a multiplicity of sectoral lanes that one can be lost in the sloughs of doctrines and wilderness of ideation not to mention the tendency towards dogmatism, monocracy and the personality cult.³⁹

Welfarism, according to Zik, is a system based on the assumption by the state, of the primary responsibility for the individual and the collective welfare of its citizens, usually by the enactment of legislation for specific public policies, such as education, health, unemployment, insurance, old age benefits, control of prices and rents, minimum wages, assistance, subsidies to agriculture, housing, and other sectors of the economy. It is particularly concerned with their implementation directly by government agencies. The main problem of welfarism is the enormous

cost involved and the mad rush of people to take advantage of free services, which make planning and budgeting very difficult.

Zik's Neo-Welfarism Provides Political and Economic Security

In the neo-welfarist society, the state monitors and directs the economic affairs for the welfare of each individual of the state. Although the government does not remove its economic interests altogether in the neo-welfarist state, it participates in making goods and services abundant and affordable for its citizens. Also the government in neo-welfarist states direct the people's participation in economic activities forestalls the exploitative tendencies of private individuals. Some individuals have the option to produce better goods of their own at affordable prices in order for them to remain in business contention.

Thus Azikiwe neo-welfarism ideology for Nigeria has far-reaching economic and political implications for the freedom of individuals as well as the society.

The political aim of this neo-welfarism is to restore democracy by building a new political leviathan where there will be political freedom, economic security and social equality⁴⁰.

The role of the state in neo-welfarism will neither be illiberalism nor autocracy anymore that it will be indifferentism. Under neo-welfarism, human beings will be like brothers, not wolves, in an atmosphere of peace, security and prosperity; the poor and weak, due to historical accident, will co-exist with their more privileged brethren without fear of enslavement. Thus neo-welfarism is a philosophy, and an ideology as well as an economic doctrine which is expected to guarantee; political, social, economic, and spiritual equilibrium, thereby marrying extended family system with the best efforts of non-Nigeria countries to safeguard freedom from ignorance; freedom from anarchy and freedom from lawlessness.

Emphasis on Education

In the war against ignorance and superstition, education should be regarded as a birthright of every Nigerian. The state should trifurcate this basic right into three segments: religious education should instill in our children moral values and ethical conduct in their relationship with fellow human beings; vocational education should train our offspring to be knowledgeable and acquire skill to adjust themselves and earn an honest living in the struggle for the survival of the fittest; continuing education should make them adaptable to their environment and inculcate in them the idea that education is a continuous process throughout life.

Religious Education: Men and Women as objects of the universe are puny. Our planet is the smallest. But our intellect has clarified the existence of spiritual forces which activate the relationship of human beings. An essence of this spirituality is the distinction between what is right and what is wrong. The role of religious education is to stress goodness, honesty, truth, love, faithfulness, fair-play and all the sterling qualities which place human beings above beasts and the other objects of creation.

Therefore, religious education must permeate through all the stages of our educational system, from the primary to the secondary and the tertiary. Adolescents and adults must be influenced by religious teachings, as distinct from denominational dogma, whether of the Christian faith, or that of Islam or the tenets of animism or those of other established and unestablished religions.

Vocational Education: Every Nigerian should be entitled to obtain education without paying for it in cash but in kind. At the primary and secondary levels, students should be given education free of charge but, in return, they shall be engaged in some sort of social services and development projects in their communities.

At the secondary and tertiary levels, students should be involved in basic military training for the intermediate and upper echelon cadres of our Armed and security Forces.

Continuing Education: Since education has been defined as life itself in its totality, it is a continuous process. Human beings are finite objects in the Universe; so they are destined to be influenced by day to day experience, until they attain a stage of mental atrophy or what some would describe as physiological zero.

Therefore, the state must provide for the systematic growth and development of the mental powers of its citizens to continue their education either by studying or by observation in the form of learning, amusements or entertainments or any other type of intellectual exercise, aesthetically speaking.

In allocating responsibility for operating schools, colleges, institutes and universities, the state should not assume exclusive jurisdiction. Rather, the state, in addition to organizing and administering schools etc. at any level, should regulate minimum standards and, through the competent vigilance of inspectorates in the Federal and State Ministries of Education, ensure that such standards are scrupulously maintained; otherwise, the delinquents should be penalized.

The organization of schools should follow the following pattern, without prejudice to private ownership of schools, which means ownership by voluntary agencies, charitable institutions, private individuals, etc.

Each State in the Federation should have one university complex. Neo-welfarism imposes upon the State the obligation to provide for the continuing education of its citizens in libraries, museums, galleries, zoological sanctuaries, botanical gardens, planetariums, theatre, etc.

Inculcation of Moral Values

The neo-welfarist government shall aim at fair and equitable distribution of the country's goods among the citizens and avoid the situation whereby some citizens are extremely rich while others are extremely poor. The state shall assume the responsibility of providing the citizens with the essential social services. The moral values under neo-welfarism, hospital treatment should be free, including the supply of drugs, x-ray examination, physiotherapy treatment, etc., but excluding the supply of dentures, optical and other surgical appliances.

Physicians and paramedical staff should be deployed to be available in all hospitals twenty-four hours of day and night⁴¹.

Here, the citizens shall enjoy the right to shelter because "shelter is coterminous with human life. Just as water, food, and raiment is essential for healthy living, so is shelter⁴². Education shall be considered as a birthright and it shall be free. But it shall not be the monopoly of the state; private ownership of schools by voluntary agencies, charitable organizations, and individuals shall be allowed. Under neo-welfarism, the state shall assume the responsibility of providing employment for every citizen that is capable of working, and of rehabilitating the handicapped, the impoverished, and the destitute in the society.

Neo-Welfarism an Ideology for Development in Nigeria

Just as it has been seen in the view of some philosophers, about the development of a society, Zik in his political thoughts has also said that development should be primarily grounded on the people. The people should not only be the means of development but also those who will enhance the development. The existence of a given state depends on the ability of the people to mobilize and galvanize them towards development. Development as we know is not just a project but is a process. Development is the process by which people create and recreate themselves and their circumstances to realize higher civilization in accordance with one's own choice and values.

Development should not be followed as a programme or project but should be followed as a process that empowers the people to create and recreate themselves in pursuit of a higher developed society that is a better life.

Neo-welfarism as a suitable system for Nigeria development, according to Azikiwe, should be based on two schools of thought: eclecticism and pragmatism which themselves are based on rationalism and empiricism. Its eclectic foundation is in the fact that “it elements in capitalism, socialism and welfarism that can be adapted to the Nigerian situation and experience”⁴³.

Nigeria can, through the eclectic methods, which are equally welfarist, adopt the best elements of this known ideology and re-orientate its primordial ideology. It aims essentially at the utility of doctrines.

The other basic system for neo-welfarism is pragmatism-“a philosophical theory dealing with things which are real, against intellectual speculation. Its historical development has been influenced by four factors: psychological, logical, ethical, and religious”⁴⁴.

Neo-welfarism founded on eclecticism and pragmatism, therefore, shifts and synchronizes into a social matrix the best elements from capitalism, socialism and welfarism.

It permits private enterprises, but invites the state to participate and collaborate in their management, control and sponsorship in order to achieve the best welfare for the people and development in Nigeria.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

SUMMARY

In so far as questions still arise concerning neo-welfarism and other ideologies, it means that none of it may be said to be a perfect ideologies, therefore it is altogether error-proof. I doubt if any of these ideologies can bring man together in a difficult state of living in a social life. More so, the society keeps on changing with new realities and new circumstances, but the Nigeria condition under which Azikiwe speculated and postulated his neo-welfarism is quite discrete from the Nigeria of today *the twenty-first century*, which is trying to keep the rate if movements with the recent socio-economic and political globalization.

Azikiwe’s ideology is academically satisfactory and theoretically relevant, though Azikiwe may not be the only available ideological option; nonetheless, it is a veritable springboard for further

thinking on ideological imperatives for Nigeria's true development. In this work, we have been able to x-ray the ideologies of Azikiwe options for development of Africa, with particular reference to Nigeria.

Conclusion

Conclusively, having examined the Neo-welfarist option by Nnamdi Azikiwe, and his ideologies that can aid the global socio-political crisis in Africa, with particular reference to Nigeria. We stand to assess that Zik did well in his ideologies, by firstly having his continent and country at heart, and for thinking of the means of developing Africa and Nigeria.

I also agree with the Azikiwe stand point of social amenities to be provided to every member of the country to make life easier and good going. And also the individual ownership of property so that we will not only depend on what the government will do for us. But we could also help enhance and promote the economic growth of our dear nation. Finally, one may note that Azikiwe's neo-welfarism could be an answer to the confused political set-ups in most African states caused by colonial and other influences. As a viable system, it could restore the basis for a genuine African socio-political life, by allowing the positive and workable principles of capitalism, socialism and welfarism to fecundate the root-principles native to African culture.

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